

Synthesis and characterization of some binuclear complexes of bis(acetylacetonato)aluminiumdi(μ -isopropoxo)di(isopropoxo)aluminium(III) with dialkyldithiophosphoric acid[†]

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Manuscript received 31 January 2014, accepted 10 February 2014

Abstract : Reactions of $[(CH_3COCHCOCH_3)_2Al(\mu-OPr^i)_2Al(OPr^i)_2]$ with $[(RO)_2P(S)SH]$ in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios in refluxing anhydrous benzene yield binuclear complexes of the type, $[(CH_3COCHCOCH_3)_2Al(\mu-OPr^i)_2Al\{S(S)P(OR)_2\}OPr^i]$ and $[(CH_3COCHCOCH_3)_2Al(\mu-OPr^i)_2Al\{S(S)P(OR)_2\}_2]$ (where R = $-CH_3$, $-C_2H_5$, $-C_4H_9$ or $-C_3H_7$), respectively. Elemental analyses, molecular weight measurements and FT-IR, 1H and ^{13}C NMR studies corroborate the formation the binuclear complexes.

Keywords : Dialkyldithiophosphoric acid, acetylacetonato, binuclear complexes of aluminum(III).

Introduction

Metal chelates of β -diketones¹⁻³ including fluorinated 1,3-diketones⁴ and related compounds⁵ exhibit fascinating structural variations. Single crystal X-ray diffraction studies of $[Al(OPr^i)(et_2acac)_2]_2$ ⁶ and $[C_6H_4O\{CH=N(C_6H_5)\}]_2Al(\mu-OPr^i)_2Al(OPr^i)_2$ ⁷, suggest that binuclear metallo-organic complexes of bidentate chelating ligands usually adopt unsymmetrical structure (1) containing aluminium atoms in the four and six coordination environment, rather than a symmetric five coordinate structure :

It has also been shown that the basic unit (1) is quite stable to further nucleophilic attack during its reactions

with a variety of ligands like β -diketones⁸⁻¹⁰, oximes^{9,11}, glycols¹²⁻¹⁴, thioglycols⁸, 8-hydroxyquinoline^{15,16}, Schiff bases^{17,18} etc. Only the terminal isopropoxy groups are being replaced without disturbing the stable unit (1). It would be interesting to mention here that aluminium being a hard acid is expected to bond strongly with hard (O/N) rather than soft (S) bases. This is evinced by the publication of only a few papers on aluminium(III) derivatives with sulphur containing ligands¹⁹⁻²⁶.

Herein, we report the synthesis and characterization of some binuclear complexes of bis(acetylacetonato)di(μ -isopropoxo)di(isopropoxo)aluminium(III) with dialkyldithiophosphoric acid.

Results and discussion

Reactions of the precursor $[(CH_3COCHCOCH_3)_2Al(\mu-OPr^i)_2Al(OPr^i)_2]$ with $[(RO)_2P(S)SH]$ in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratio in refluxing anhydrous benzene led to the formation of $[(CH_3COCHCOCH_3)_2Al(\mu-OPr^i)_2Al\{S(S)P(OR)_2\}(OPr^i)]$ and $[(CH_3COCHCOCH_3)_2Al(\mu-OPr^i)_2Al\{S(S)P(OR)_2\}_2]$, respectively :

[†]In honour of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

(where R = -CH₃, C₂H₅, C₄H₉ⁱ or C₃H₇ⁱ; n = 1 or 2)

These reactions are quite facile and quantitative. The liberated isopropanol could be removed readily in 4 h as an azeotrope. The progress of the reactions was monitored by estimating the liberated isopropanol present in the azeotrope, oxidimetrically. All these derivatives are yellow viscous solids, hygroscopic in nature and are soluble in common organic solvents (benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride etc.). The molecular weight measurements indicate their dimeric nature in refluxing anhydrous benzene.

IR spectra :

The tentative assignments of some of the important bands have been made and is summarized in Table 1. The band due to νS-H at about 2500 cm⁻¹ in the dialkyldithiophosphoric acid, disappears in the corresponding aluminium(III) complexes, indicating bonding of the sulphur to aluminium(III) atom. Medium intensity band in

the region 925–990 cm⁻¹ due to ν(P-O-C), in the parent acids, do not show any significant shift in the aluminium(III) complexes²⁷. Bands due to ν(P=S) at 650–685 cm⁻¹ show a considerable downfield shift (~10–20 cm⁻¹) in the aluminium(III) complexes indicating the possibility of bidentate attachment of the ligand to the metal atom^{27,28}.

The presence of strong bands in the region 1600–1615 and 1500–1545 cm⁻¹ due to ν(C=O) and ν(C=C) stretching vibrations, respectively, suggests the bidentate quasi-aromatic nature of the acetylacetonate moiety^{29,30}.

Medium intensity bands observed in the region 1000–1020 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes may be assigned to ν(C-O) of the isopropoxy group²⁹. A band at 520–550 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to be ν(Al-S)⁸. The Al-O-Al vibration have been observed⁸ in the region 750–775 cm⁻¹.

¹H NMR spectra :

The important signals in ¹H NMR spectra of all these derivatives are summarized in Table 2. A comparison of the spectra of the free ligands with the spectra of the corresponding derivatives shows absence of broad signal due to -SH group of the dialkyldithiophosphoric acid indicating deprotonation of the ligands and formation of Al-S bond⁸. The methine protons of the bridging and terminal isopropoxy groups get merged to give multiplet

Table 1. IR spectral data (cm⁻¹) of [(CH₃COCHCOCH₃)₂Al(μ-OPrⁱ)₂Al{S(S)P(OR)₂}_n(OPrⁱ)_{2-2n}] and [(CH₃COCHCOCH₃)₂Al(μ-OPrⁱ)₂Al{S(S)P(OR)₂}₂]

Sr. No.	Complex	Acetylacetonate moiety		Isopropoxy moiety		Dialkyldithiophosphate moiety			
		ν(C=O)	ν(C=C)	ν(C-O)	ν(P=S)	ν(P-O-C)	ν(Al-O-Al)	ν(Al-O)	ν(Al-S)
1.	[(CH ₃ COCHCOCH ₃) ₂ Al(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ Al{S(S)P(OCH ₃) ₂ } ₂ (OPr ⁱ)] (1)	1605s	1520s	1010m	680w	950m	775w	625w	540w
2.	[(CH ₃ COCHCOCH ₃) ₂ Al(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ Al{S(S)P(OCH ₃) ₂ } ₂] (2)	1605s	1500s	1015m	685w	925m	775w	625w	530w
3.	[(CH ₃ COCHCOCH ₃) ₂ Al(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ Al{S(S)P(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂ } ₂ (OPr ⁱ)] (3)	1600s	1535s	1020m	655w	975m	755w	635w	530w
4.	[(CH ₃ COCHCOCH ₃) ₂ Al(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ Al{S(S)P(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂ } ₂] (4)	1605s	1525s	1005m	660w	975m	760w	620w	535w
5.	[(CH ₃ COCHCOCH ₃) ₂ Al(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ Al{S(S)P(OC ₄ H ₉) ₂ } ₂ (OPr ⁱ)] (5)	1605s	1520s	1010m	670w	975m	750w	625w	550w
6.	[(CH ₃ COCHCOCH ₃) ₂ Al(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ Al{S(S)P(OC ₄ H ₉) ₂ } ₂] (6)	1615s	1525s	1005m	650w	990m	750w	630w	525w
7.	[(CH ₃ COCHCOCH ₃) ₂ Al(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ Al{S(S)P(OC ₃ H ₇) ₂ } ₂ (OPr ⁱ)] (7)	1605s	1540s	1000m	685w	990m	775w	620w	520w
8.	[(CH ₃ COCHCOCH ₃) ₂ Al(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ Al{S(S)P(OC ₃ H ₇) ₂ } ₂] (8)	1610s	1545s	1005m	680w	995m	770w	625w	530w

Table 2. ^1H NMR spectral data (δ ppm) of $[(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOCH}_3)_2\text{Al}(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al}\{\text{S}(\text{S})\text{P}(\text{OR})_2\}(\text{OPr}^i)]$ and $[(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOCH}_3)_2\text{Al}(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al}\{\text{S}(\text{S})\text{P}(\text{OR})_2\}_2]$

Sr. No.	Complex	Acetylacetonate moiety		Isopropoxy moiety		Dialkyl/dithiophosphate moiety		
		-CH ₃	-CH<	-CH ₃	-OCH<	-CH ₃	-CH ₂	-CH
1.	$[(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOCH}_3)_2\text{Al}(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al}\{\text{S}(\text{S})\text{P}(\text{OCH}_3)_2\}(\text{OPr}^i)]$ (1)	1.88 (12H, s)	5.41 (2H, s)	1.20 (12H, d), 1.23 (6H, d)	3.15-3.51 (3H, m)	3.56 (6H, s)	-	-
2.	$[(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOCH}_3)_2\text{Al}(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al}\{\text{S}(\text{S})\text{P}(\text{OCH}_3)_2\}_2]$ (2)	1.88 (12H, s)	5.38 (2H, s)	1.19 (12H, d)	3.25, (2H, m)	3.54 (12H, s)	-	-
3.	$[(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOCH}_3)_2\text{Al}(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al}\{\text{S}(\text{S})\text{P}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_2\}(\text{OPr}^i)]$ (3)	1.95 (12H, s)	5.70 (2H, s)	1.22 (12H, d), 1.25 (6H, d)	3.75-3.90 (3H, m)	1.37 (6H, t)	4.39-4.71 (4H, m)	-
4.	$[(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOCH}_3)_2\text{Al}(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al}\{\text{S}(\text{S})\text{P}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_2\}_2]$ (4)	1.99 (12H, s)	5.51 (2H, s)	1.27 (12H, d)	3.99, (2H, m)	1.39 (12H, t)	4.40-4.79 (8H, m)	-
5.	$[(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOCH}_3)_2\text{Al}(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al}\{\text{S}(\text{S})\text{P}(\text{OC}_4\text{H}_9)_2\}(\text{OPr}^i)]$ (5)	1.84 (12H, s)	5.48 (2H, s)	1.26 (12H, d), 1.28 (6H, d)	3.62-4.04 (3H, m)	1.19 (12H, d)	4.49-4.68 (4H, m)	1.90-2.54 (2H, m)
6.	$[(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOCH}_3)_2\text{Al}(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al}\{\text{S}(\text{S})\text{P}(\text{OC}_4\text{H}_9)_2\}_2]$ (6)	1.88 (12H, s)	5.37 (2H, s)	1.24 (12H, d)	3.68, (2H, m)	1.19 (24H, d)	4.52-4.62 (8H, m)	1.91-2.04 (4H, m)
7.	$[(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOCH}_3)_2\text{Al}(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al}\{\text{S}(\text{S})\text{P}(\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7)_2\}(\text{OPr}^i)]$ (7)	1.89 (12H, s)	5.64 (2H, s)	1.20 (12H, d), 1.22 (6H, d)	3.48-4.07 (3H, m)	1.15 (12H, d)	-	4.59-4.64 (2H, m)
8.	$[(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOCH}_3)_2\text{Al}(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al}\{\text{S}(\text{S})\text{P}(\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7)_2\}_2]$ (8)	1.87 (12H, s)	5.36 (2H, s)	1.22 (12H, d)	3.45, (2H, m)	1.11 (24H, d)	-	4.60-4.75 (4H, m)

in the range 3.15–4.07 ppm³¹. The methyl protons of the bridging isopropoxy groups appear at 1.19–1.27 ppm, while the methyl protons of the terminal isopropoxy groups appear at 1.22–1.28 ppm as a doublets, indicating the nonequivalent nature of the bridging and terminal isopropoxy groups¹⁸.

The methyl and the methine signals of the acetylacetonate moieties appeared at 1.83–1.99 and 5.36–5.70 ppm, respectively¹⁸.

^{13}C NMR spectra :

The ^{13}C NMR spectra of aluminum(III) complexes (Table 3) confirmed the mode of bonding as indicates by ^1H NMR spectra.

The signal at 26.4–26.9, 100.3–101.4 and 191.0–191.6 ppm may be assigned to methyl, methine and carbonyl carbon of the acetylacetonate moieties, respectively.

Characteristic chemical shift values of the isopropoxy groups observed at 23.7–25.6 and 63.1–64.9 ppm have been assigned to the methyl and methine carbons, respectively.

Similarly, presence of two signals each for the methyl and the methine carbons of the bridging and terminal isopropoxy groups indicate nonequivalent nature of the isopropoxy groups in these derivatives.

The ^{27}Al NMR spectrum of $[(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOCH}_3)_2\text{Al}(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al}\{\text{S}(\text{S})\text{P}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_2\}_2]$ exhibits only a sharp signal at 1.09 ppm indicating that both the metal atoms are in hexa-coordination environment.

^{31}P NMR spectrum of $[(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOCH}_3)_2\text{Al}(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al}\{\text{S}(\text{S})\text{P}(\text{OCH}_3)_2\}(\text{OPr}^i)]$ in CDCl_3 , exhibits only one resonance signal at 78.9 ppm indicating tetra-coordination around the phosphorus atom.

On the basis of the above studies, possible structure for these derivatives may be proposed (Fig. 1).

Experimental

Materials and method :

All manipulations were carried out under strictly anhydrous condition using anhydrous CaCl_2 guard/side tubes. The solvents were purified and dried according to the standard procedures. Due precautions were taken while handling hazardous chemicals and solvents such as benzene. Aluminium was estimated gravimetrically as the

Fig. 1. Proposed structures of (a) $[(CH_3COCHCOCH_3)_2Al(\mu-OPr^i)_2Al\{S(S)P(OR)_2\}(OPr^i)]$ and (b) $[(CH_3COCHCOCH_3)_2Al(\mu-OPr^i)_2Al\{S(S)P(OR)_2\}_2]$, respectively (where R = $-CH_3$, $-C_2H_5$, C_4H_9 or C_3H_7).

oxinate²⁹. Sulphur was estimated by the Messenger's method³². Isopropanol (Merck, Germany) was estimated by the chromate oxidimetric method³³. The starting material $[(acac)_2Al(\mu-OPr^i)_2Al(OPr^i)_2]$ was prepared by the reported method¹³. IR spectra were recorded as Nujol mulls on a Nicolet Magna 550 spectrometer in the range 4000–400 cm^{-1} . 1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on a JEOL FX 90Q spectrometer using TMS as an inter-

nal reference in $CDCl_3$ and $CHCl_3$, respectively. The ^{27}Al NMR spectrum was carried out in toluene using aluminium nitrate as an external reference in aqueous solution and ^{31}P NMR spectrum was recorded in $CDCl_3$. The molecular weight measurements were carried out by the elevation in boiling point method using a Beckmann thermometer fitted in a glass assembly (supplied by JSGW, India) in anhydrous benzene.

Table 3. ^{13}C NMR spectral data (δ ppm) of $[(CH_3COCHCOCH_3)_2Al(\mu-OPr^i)_2Al\{S(S)P(OR)_2\}(OPr^i)]$ and $[(CH_3COCHCOCH_3)_2Al(\mu-OPr^i)_2Al\{S(S)P(OR)_2\}_2]$

Sr. No.	Complex	Acetylacetonate moiety			Isopropoxy moiety		Dialkyldithiophosphate moiety		
		-CH ₃	-CH	-C=O	-CH ₂	-OCH	-CH ₃	-CH ₂	-CH
1.	$[(CH_3COCHCOCH_3)_2Al(\mu-OPr^i)_2Al\{S(S)P(OCH_3)_2\}(OPr^i)]$ (1)	26.9	100.3	191.1, 24.9	25.6, 63.8	64.5	54.7	-	-
2.	$[(CH_3COCHCOCH_3)_2Al(\mu-OPr^i)_2Al\{S(S)P(OCH_3)_2\}_2]$ (2)	26.5	101.3	191.0	25.5	64.2	54.8	-	-
3.	$[(CH_3COCHCOCH_3)_2Al(\mu-OPr^i)_2Al\{S(S)P(OC_2H_5)_2\}(OPr^i)]$ (3)	26.8	100.7	191.4	25.4, 24.8	63.7, 63.9	15.8	64.6	-
4.	$[(CH_3COCHCOCH_3)_2Al(\mu-OPr^i)_2Al\{S(S)P(OC_2H_5)_2\}_2]$ (4)	26.4	100.8	191.2	25.0	64.1	15.5	64.3	-
5.	$[(CH_3COCHCOCH_3)_2Al(\mu-OPr^i)_2Al\{S(S)P(OC_4H_9)_2\}(OPr^i)]$ (5)	26.5	100.9	191.3	25.4, 24.8	64.3, 63.1	18.9	74.1	28.8
6.	$[(CH_3COCHCOCH_3)_2Al(\mu-OPr^i)_2Al\{S(S)P(OC_4H_9)_2\}_2]$ (6)	26.7	101.4	191.5	25.6	64.4	18.6	74.5	28.7
7.	$[(CH_3COCHCOCH_3)_2Al(\mu-OPr^i)_2Al\{S(S)P(OC_3H_7)_2\}(OPr^i)]$ (7)	26.6	100.8	191.6	25.6, 23.7	64.9, 63.7	23.5	-	73.8
8.	$[(CH_3COCHCOCH_3)_2Al(\mu-OPr^i)_2Al\{S(S)P(OC_3H_7)_2\}_2]$ (8)	26.6	100.6	191.3	25.4	63.9	23.8	-	73.9

Reactants (g)		Product	Colour and physical state	Yield (%)	Pr-OH (g) Found (Calcd.)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			Molecular weight :	
A	B					Al	OPr ⁱ	S	Found (Calcd.)	Found (Calcd.)
2.35	0.77 R = OMe	[(CH ₃ COCHCOCH ₃) ₂ Al(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ Al{(S(S)P(OR) ₂)} ₂ Al{(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ Al{(S(S)P(OR) ₂)} ₂]	Yellow viscous solid	96.4	0.29 (0.29)	9.10 (9.2)	29.81 (30.91)	10.20 (10.90)	539 (586.24)	
2.36	1.54 R = OMe	[(CH ₃ COCHCOCH ₃) ₂ Al(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ Al{(S(S)P(OR) ₂)} ₂]	Yellow viscous solid	99.9	0.52 (0.58)	7.70 (7.89)	17.00 (17.24)	18.11 (18.70)	640 (684.14)	
2.87	1.11 R = OC ₂ H ₅	[(CH ₃ COCHCOCH ₃) ₂ Al(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ Al{(S(S)P(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂)} ₂ Al{(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ Al{(S(S)P(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂)} ₂]	Yellow viscous solid	99.4	0.34 (0.35)	8.3 (8.70)	28.2 (28.80)	10.01 (10.40)	600 (614.24)	
2.44	1.87 R = OC ₂ H ₅	[(CH ₃ COCHCOCH ₃) ₂ Al(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ Al{(S(S)P(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂)} ₂]	Yellow viscous solid	99.8	0.55 (0.59)	7.01 (7.20)	15.49 (15.94)	17.02 (17.29)	789 (740.14)	
3.31	1.67 R = OC ₄ H ₉ ⁱ	[(CH ₃ COCHCOCH ₃) ₂ Al(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ Al{(S(S)P(OC ₄ H ₉) ₂)} ₂ Al{(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ Al{(S(S)P(OC ₄ H ₉) ₂)} ₂]	Yellow viscous solid	100	0.39 (0.40)	7.99 (8.02)	26.00 (26.39)	9.26 (9.50)	650 (670.57)	
3.16	3.18 R = OC ₄ H ₉ ^j	[(CH ₃ COCHCOCH ₃) ₂ Al(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ Al{(S(S)P(OC ₄ H ₉) ₂)} ₂]	Yellow viscous solid	98	0.70 (0.77)	6.4 (6.30)	13.41 (13.83)	14.90 (15.00)	800 (852.80)	
2.50	1.15 R = OC ₃ H ₇ ⁱ	[(CH ₃ COCHCOCH ₃) ₂ Al(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ Al{(S(S)P(OC ₃ H ₇) ₂)} ₂ Al{(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ Al{(S(S)P(OC ₃ H ₇) ₂)} ₂]	Yellow viscous solid	99	0.29 (0.30)	8.11 (8.40)	45.09 (45.95)	9.90 (10.00)	610 (641.9)	
3.19	2.84 R = OC ₃ H ₇ ^j	[(CH ₃ COCHCOCH ₃) ₂ Al(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ Al{(S(S)P(OC ₃ H ₇) ₂)} ₂]	Yellow viscous solid	94	0.71 (0.78)	6.67 (6.78)	44.02 (44.07)	15.95 (16.08)	750 (795.96)	

Preparation of $[(CH_3COCHCOCH_3)_2Al(\mu-OPr^i)_2Al\{S(S)P(OCH_3)_2\}(OPr^i)]$:

The reaction mixture containing $[(CH_3COCHCOCH_3)_2Al(\mu-OPr^i)_2Al(OPr^i)_2]$ (2.35 g) and $[(CH_3O)_2P(S)SH]$ (0.77 g) in 1 : 1 molar ratio in anhydrous benzene (~60 mL) was refluxed for 4 h under a fractionating column. The liberated isopropanol was continuously fractionated out azeotropically with benzene. The progress as well as the completion of the reaction was checked by the estimation of the isopropanol in the azeotrope by oxidimetric titration. After stripping off the excess solvent under reduced pressure, a yellow viscous compound was obtained. The purification as well as the formation of good quality crystals of the compound from a mixture of dichloromethane and *n*-hexane (1 : 1) could not be achieved. Rest of the members of the series were prepared using the same general procedure and their analytical data are summarized in Table 4.

Conclusion

Formation of unsymmetrical binuclear complexes containing aluminium atoms in different coordination environments is possible. The present findings indicate scope for a detail study in this direction.

Acknowledgement

We thank DST, New Delhi for financial support. Nikita Sharma and Ram Gopal are grateful to UGC, New Delhi for the postdoctoral and UPE fellowships.

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